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Superheroes and Social Realism: Exploring Power, Desire, and Reality in Samit Basu's *Turbulence*

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Abstract:

Samit Basu, an acclaimed Indian English novelist, has chosen science fiction and fantasy as the primary mediums for his literary expression. Science and fantasy have provided the broadest possible scope for the exercise of imagination and for communicating serious themes in a light tone. The paper attempts to study Samit Basu's *Turbulence*, in which he sets his superhero novel in India and interprets it in a modern way rooted in urban fantasy. The novel is set within a socio-realistic framework, where four hundred and three passengers boarding a flight from London to Delhi discover superpowers within themselves and realize that these are directly connected to their innermost desires and aspirations. Samit Basu has carefully crafted the superpowers and executed them in a much better manner in the novel while debating the ethical exercise of Power. The varied characters uncover their superpowers towards the various problems in the present Indian society and thus bring out the author's intention to social realism. The paper will also discuss Basu's postmodern perspective on the superhero genre, wherein he endeavors to articulate and interrogate the defining characteristics of superheroes and their relation to the concepts of nationalism and humanity.

Keywords: Superhero, Social Criticism, Power Exercise, Nationalism, Humanity.

Samit Basu is considered one of the earliest and leading Indian novelists to write in Science Fiction and fantasy modes. His literary trajectory reflects a clear influence of canonical works, particularly *The Hobbit*, *The Lord of the Rings*, and *The Hitchhiker's Guide to the Galaxy*. He acknowledges the *Discworld* series as a foundational influence on his debut novel, *The Simoqin Prophecies* (2004), which is regarded as India's first work of science fiction and fantasy (SFF) in English. Over the years, he has penned several notable SFF novels such as *Turbulence*, *Resistance*, *Terror on the Titanic*, *Chosen Spirits*, and *The City Inside*.

Samit Basu's *Turbulence* (2012) is among the earliest Indian English novels in the superhero genre; it won Wired's Goldenbot Award as one of the best books of 2012 and was named Book of the Year 2013 by *superheronovels.com*. Basu has played a pioneering role in shaping the Indian superhero narrative, providing a cohesive and inclusive representation of this mode of fiction. An exploration of the origins of the superhero genre reveals that it first consolidated within the medium of comic books. By the late 1930s, comic books had become the primary platform for developing and popularizing superhero narratives, emerging as the most commercially successful genre for leading publishers of the time. While comic books provided the framework within which the superhero genre matured and flourished, its deeper roots can be traced to classical mythology. The hero's journey, along with traits such as extraordinary physique, superhuman powers, hidden identities, and epic death-defying feats in classical mythology, underscores the superhero genre's reliance on these ancient narrative patterns and motifs. The term 'superhero' emerged around 1917, but gained significant traction with the publication of *Superman* in 1938. This era witnessed a surge in superhero characters, including

Batman and Wonder Woman, who often reflected the societal issues of their time, such as World War II and the Great Depression.

Peter Coogan identifies four principal elements that define the Superhero genre: mission, power, identity and costume. *Turbulence* encompasses nearly all the defining features of the superhero genre so convincingly that it can indisputably be classified as superhero fiction. The novel embraces the very formula of superhero narratives, i.e. origin story, discovery and acceptance of superpowers, grouping of the heroes, inevitable rise of one key villain and his lesser-powered followers, and ultimately the battle for the future of humanity with some hilarious dialogues. Basu masterfully constructs action scenes, vividly depicting superheroes, their powers, and combat strategies with striking imagery, while his distinctive style lends authenticity, rendering the narrative a naturalistic portrayal of the superhero genre. The novel is an urban fantasy that vividly highlights the socio-economic realities of contemporary India.

The narrative focuses on a group of Indian passengers, along with Uzma, a British-Pakistani character, who travel on a flight from London to Delhi. All individuals aboard the flight inexplicably develop extraordinary new abilities. The protagonist, Aman Sen, advances the hypothesis that each person has acquired power that corresponds, in some manner, to their innermost desires. For example, Aman, who once felt isolated and lost in a city where contacts and connections meant everything, can now instantly access any communication network using only his mind. He is constantly online, able to hack any secure system, listen to any phone conversation, and remain connected to the entire world. He informs, “My powers let me hook up to anything on the network- computers, phones, satellites, all sorts of stuff” (53). Aman aspires to be an old-fashioned superhero who seeks to communicate with others in order to save the

world, but later discovers a villain named Jai Mathur, born out of the same superhuman abilities, who is harming superheroes. Jai desires to rule the world under a military regime, killing all who do not agree with him. Uzma, an aspiring Bollywood Actress, possesses boundless attractiveness and can make everyone adore her. Tia narrates her story, "My in-laws were horrible, and I used to dream about having many other lives, going to an office instead of sitting at home all day, being a teacher, being a dancer, an actress, a cricketer- anything else" (55). Consequently, her power is to copy herself. At any given time, there can be many Tias, all identical to the original. Another leading character is Vir, an Indian Air Force Pilot, who can fly unlike anyone. Namrata is the mob manipulator. She reveals, "I was sick of covering stupid fashion shows and awards ceremonies. Maybe that's why I got this power. I could rustle up a mob, make them really mad about anything I wanted. Mad enough to rip apart anything I asked them to"(301).

Fantasy and science fiction inherently challenge both the characters' convictions and the readers' rational frameworks, requiring the adoption of a stance of 'willing suspension of disbelief' in order to fully appreciate and engage with their imaginative possibilities. Uzma expresses her realistic doubt about this supernatural happening, "Do you have any idea how we got these powers?"(60). Aman gives a very generic reply, "None whatsoever. Aliens, Wizards, gods, trans-humanists, evolutionary accident, virus, secret societies, Republicans, Apple designers- you take your pick. We don't know how, where, what or why- or whether this has happened before" (60). Supernatural powers are a subject of exercise, whose origin and development lie beyond the boundaries of rational scrutiny. Aman has an intention to unite all the superheroes due to a supposed danger. Tia reveals to Uzma:

The truth is, we're all in danger. A lot of the people on that flight are dead or missing. . . . Twenty-four people were on transfer flights or left India within a day. Someone hunted them down. Killed each and every one of them. All over the world, from Hong Kong to Toronto. (56-57)

Aman suspects that some of the superheroes are being held at Udhampur, with both Air Force officers and high-level officials involved. Aman thinks, "This operation's being run by a few people, probably Indian, high up enough in the military or the government to arm-twist other people into organizing a large police operation, but it's all very hush- hush" (57). Aman reveals his generic superhero plan, "Essentially, we keep ourselves safe, find other people with powers, and then we make the world a better place" (61). But Vir, who is working under Jai Mathur, shows unwavering faith in him. Aman questions Vir about the Kashmir base and asks, "How many of us are you holding there?" (71). He expresses his ignorance, but Aman convinces him that Jai is running a criminal business and it is not state-sanctioned. Jai has removed or killed all the foreigners who were on the plane and is still searching for the remaining ones. Samit Basu silently highlights the thinking of criminals and gangsters who are not ready to absorb any kind of intervention in their criminal estates. The superhumans who resist are subject to being killed. Tia reflects, "If- *when*- we're discovered, people aren't going to be happy about our existence. Especially if we're a threat to them, and we definitely are"(75). Aman expresses his purpose of uniting all the heroes to address planetary problems and control villainous activities, which is a rather common intention among superheroes. Basu highlights the contemporary global problems that his superheroes would like to resolve positively:

Can you imagine what we could achieve together? With just a small bunch of us, we could change everything. We could stop global warming, make the Sahara a

rice bowl, save endangered animals, stop genocide, find alternatives to oil, and stop the demand recession. The kind of things superheroes would do in comics....

(76)

Samit Basu, through Sunder's new socio-historical, cultural, scientific, and psychological theory, affirms that the origin of superhero novels is not wholly imaginary but rather connected to real life and human needs. Sunder claims:

The fundamental premise is that heroic myths and legends through the course of human history are all true- possibly exaggerated by enthusiastic re-tellers, especially the bits about gods and monsters, but the demigod heroes in their stories are actually existed. And these heroes from Hercules to Sherlock Holmes, appeared because of these legends: the legends were not records of their actions, but prophetic texts derived from collective human aspirations that paved the way for their arrival. (84)

Sunder argues that legendary heroes emerged in response to profound human aspirations during times of suffering, offering societies a sense of relief and inspiration amid their struggles. This perspective constitutes a foundational approach adopted by many SFF authors. Furthermore, Samit Basu also points out the generic feature of Superhero narratives. It is the human imagination and dreams that paved the way for inventions and progress:

It is the same with stories of heroes: humanity's dreams of a more-than-mortal saviour, expressed through fictions whether oral or printed, led at some point to the manifestation of new cultural heroes- evolutionary forerunners empowered by mysterious agents. (84)

The argument between Jai and Vir on the subject of power exercise highlights the central discourse of this novel. The exercise of Power should be under the purview of humanity. The Wing Commander interrogates Jai regarding his objectives and the rationale for establishing a clandestine base. Gradually, the confrontation escalates into a physical altercation, and while Vir attempts to strike Jai but fails, Tariq—Jai’s associate—kills five military personnel loyal to the Wing Commander. Eventually, Jai discloses his overarching plan:

Thanks to this strange incident, there are powers that exist now that can make India—and only India—the mightiest nation in the world. . . . I am going to kill every powered individual I cannot use. I do this not for myself, but for my country (105).

Jai’s intention reveals a ruthless determination to harness extraordinary abilities for the sole benefit of India, irrespective of the human cost. His vision includes eliminating all perceived military threats—first from neighboring Pakistan and China, and eventually from the United States of America. Under his leadership, a scientific division focuses on experiments involving genetic manipulation and transplantation to manufacture superhuman capabilities. Jai’s ultimate desire is to become the greatest warrior in the world, deploying his enhanced powers to dominate and reshape the global order according to his nationalistic ideals. His companion Jerry can launch an electromagnetic pulse that shuts down all nearby systems for several minutes. Tariq, with the help of Google Earth, can travel anywhere he wishes. Amina is described as an evil flying muscle monster. Jai is using Afghan prisoners for experiments on their bodies. Jai reveals, “We’re still working on it. Simple processes like blood transfusions or organ exchange haven’t yet produced any powered humans. But we’ll crack it eventually” (108). Jai’s worldview is narrowly confined within a rigid military mindset, reflecting a conception of nationalism that

prioritises domination and control over human values. Basu, in contrast, foregrounds the principles of humanity and an inclusive form of nationalism rooted in the Indian philosophy of *Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam*, which envisions the entire world as a single family and upholds the individuality of each human being irrespective of race, religion, or other differences. From this perspective, the indiscriminate killing of civilians or adversaries to advance a narrow nationalist agenda is fundamentally unjustifiable. Basu underscores that beyond the confines of nation-states, what ought to prevail are the universal values of compassion and love. Vir emerges as a critical voice against Jai's militaristic project. He laments: "Oh, this endless war, this senseless violence!" (112). He further reflects on the cyclical and futile nature of human conflict: "People are fighting for millennia over nothing! If only someone had thought of this before! We could all get together and make the world perfect!" (112). Vir's idealism is emblematic of Basu's broader humanistic ideology, which serves as a foundation for his superhuman narratives. While acknowledging that a perfect world has never existed, Vir remains optimistic, suggesting, "I know this hasn't happened before," but insisting, "it could happen now. We're superhumans. And we all have so much in common" (112). Through Vir's hopeful rhetoric, Basu articulates a vision of collective responsibility that extends beyond familial or societal obligations to encompass the nation — and ultimately the entire human community. In contrast, Jai exemplifies a narrow, self-centred, and authoritarian mentality, intent on shaping the world according to his own restrictive and violent methods. Basu thus critiques such limited nationalism by proposing an ethic of global human solidarity, where superhuman abilities should serve not conquest but the betterment of all humanity.

Jai wanted to run the world according to his method. He complains to Vir, "We could have ruled the world together, Vir. That was what I wanted. Now I'm going to have to do it by myself"

(122). Jai recruits Namrata as his advance intelligence officer and asks her to search for Aman and his team. In response to Jai's relentless pursuit and execution of superheroes who refuse to submit to his demands, Namrata proposes an extreme countermeasure, suggesting the abduction of Jai's parents as leverage: "We should kidnap his parents and say we'll kill them if he doesn't turn himself in" (163). This proposal directly challenges the moral framework traditionally associated with superhero conduct. Aman immediately rejects Namrata's suggestion, articulating the ethical boundaries that define their identity: "We can't kidnap his parents! . . . It's not — it's not a superhero sort of thing to do" (163). This exchange underscores the tension between utilitarian strategies and the normative superhero code, reinforcing the characters' commitment to moral restraint even in the face of existential threats. Consequently, Aman and Uzma are taken hostage by Jai, intensifying the stakes of the conflict. Meanwhile, Anima kills Bob and Tia; however, Tia later reappears, complicating the narrative of loss and survival. In his conversation with Aman, Jai reveals his ambition for global military domination, a vision that exposes his megalomaniacal tendencies and aligns him with the archetype of a selfish, authoritarian villain. He further reveals to Aman, "He wants to accomplish what Genghis Khan, Alexander and Julius Caesar could not. And before people raise statues to him, he wants to build himself in the image of his idols-but does not know how" (187). Jai outlines a systematic plan for global domination with Aman's coerced assistance. Initially, he intends to dispatch a polite email to each targeted nation, requesting their surrender and later on enforcing compliance through technological subjugation. "He is to disable all communications, empty all banks, shut off power grids, block up dams, refineries, plants and pipelines" (189). Jai's imperial ambitions extend to symbolic and cultural domination, as he envisions replacing national flags with his own emblem — a saffron sun on a black background — and composing a new national anthem to consolidate his rule. His

overarching objective is to govern and control the entire world, employing strategies reminiscent of historical superpowers by manipulating resistance through the deliberate cultivation of rebels and terrorists. However, Jai regrets that his conquest cannot be carried out under India's banner. Through this characterization, Basu portrays Jai as a fanatic, thereby critiquing fanaticism itself and highlighting how it fosters hatred, intolerance, and a dangerously narrow worldview. Jai exhibits profound frustration upon confronting the inclusive and pluralistic practices of Indian civilization, "He is deeply chagrined by the fact that India has proved to be a warm, welcoming and exotic destination" (191). His militaristic worldview cannot accommodate a ruling order that functions outside his rigid, authoritarian framework. Although Jai professes a form of patriotism, his sentiments reveal a troubling distortion, as he declares, "I have a patriotic desire to see India's gangsters be the world's worst" (203). Through this portrayal, Basu interrogates the tension between genuine patriotism and dangerous fanaticism, suggesting that authentic national loyalty must operate within ethical boundaries and contribute positively to a country's global reputation. Fanaticism and pseudo-patriotism, by contrast, risk undermining the nation's standing and fostering intolerance and violence.

Basu raises a profound and pragmatic question regarding the passive attitude of people before getting supernatural power. Uzma critically reflects:

I just don't see why having these powers makes it necessary for all of us to become politicians, warriors, social workers, whatever. We should have tried it before if we really wanted to do it. None of us chose to spend our lives helping people before we got our powers- why should we do it now? (208)

It is not only the duty of superheroes to save the world from multiple challenges, but also of each common person. Instead of waiting and praying, we should try to change the world as per our capacity and reach. Basu offers a genuine and practical response to Uzma, ensuring that the integrity and significance of superheroes are not put under scrutiny. Aman replies:

“Maybe you’d feel differently if you knew how to use your powers.”... I’d never considered social work before- but maybe that was because I knew I might have helped a few people, but it would have meant sacrificing too much, and I wouldn’t really have made a significant difference. But now? Every decision we make is crucial. (208)

Vir’s statement also confirms the above thought. After digging himself out from under the ruins of Udampur base, Vir was not in the mood to save the world. He travelled across the Himalayas, visited Mount Everest, Antarctica, Mongolia, New Mexico and decided to be a travelling hero. “At some point of time-Vir is not exactly sure when–he started helping people” (243). He feels, “...-but abandoning the entire world in its hour of need? Not Vir Singh” (244). A real Superhero cannot stop helping humanity. The powers in them act as a positive force, driving them to address human needs.

The episode of Real Aman and Cyber Aman draws our attention to science fiction movies. Cyber Aman says, “He has shut down. I am running his flesh” (213). The entire episode serves as a prototype of science and fantasy fiction, wherein these genres function as both a mode and a medium to articulate repressed and unexpressed desires. Cyber Aman invites Uzma for love and intimacy which Real Aman was unable to express. Subsequently, the entire strategy devised by the heroes to counter the stigma of terrorism reflects the conceptual framework underlying the

formulation of superheroes and their associated attributes. The characters reflect that a superhero must have a costume and a badge on it. He should have a catchy name, and his actions should not be confined to a geographical boundary. Aman reacts to the idea of having the Indian flag on the badge, “you’re a global hero, not captain India. Your costume shouldn’t be anything definitely ethnic either—no kurtas, no turban” (256). Basu conveys the idea of a global hero. One’s actions and ideas should not be constrained by narrow perspectives but should instead reflect a concern for the well-being of all humanity. A hero transcends race and religion and helps all living beings in the universe. Furthermore, Basu wants to answer the real purpose of superheroes. Vir is accomplished with physical requirements and prepares his speech. Vir thinks not to say, “we are here to protect you” because citizens are hesitant towards the costumed men. Vir knows from his experience that civilians in Kashmir and the North-Eastern states do not like being protected by men in uniform. A hero is not to say, “We are here to save you” because it sounds like a televangelist. He does not feel the need to promise, like politicians, a world free from poverty, corruption, crime, and illiteracy. Ultimately, he decides to promise that superheroes are not meant to rule but to help humanity. These promises are still insufficient to fill the vacuum between civilians and superheroes. Consequently, the contest of thoughts leads towards a final solution. Basu endeavours to address and reconcile the collective psychological rupture—marked by disbelief and insecurity—that emerges with the sudden existence of superheroes. All the superheroes in the novel decide:

The only way, they decide, to make mankind as a whole see them as a potential boon is to offer them something: a world where the existence of superhumans will not make normal humans obsolete. The only real solution is to offer to give everyone superpowers; to work with human scientists to understand the nature of

their powers, and then to distribute these powers. For free.... A planet of evolved post-humans, super-smart, super-healthy, super-strong, super-fast, super-skilled, and damn the consequences. (261)

Basu anticipates a utopian world of skilled civilians. No one is going to be a victim where all are super-humans. He envisions an identical distribution of power and characteristics to avoid unjust hierarchy and humiliation, which is prevalent throughout the world. Ultimately, the formulaic theme—that virtue should be rewarded and vice punished—comes into play. Power corrupts Jai; he becomes impulsive and narcissistic. Vir warns, “You have to answer for your crimes” (317). Thereupon, Jai remarks, “Nothing we do is a crime. We are gods among mortals, Vir. Try and wrap your thick head around that” (317). Now, all the superheroes unite and make a successful plan to curb and control the monstrous plan of Jai. The story ends with a satisfactory and desirable finish where Jai is defeated and removed from the scene.

The novel also highlights the socio-economic reality of contemporary society. Women have been the vulnerable victims of a patriarchal societal setup. Women are increasingly involved in various fields, but still they face issues like gender discrimination, violence, and economic inequality. The story of Tia is the average story of all Indian women. Tia was unhappy because her in-laws were horrible. She wanted to go to the office instead of sitting at home all day. She reflects, “ I talked my husband’s family into letting me go to work, but it was so difficult to manage the house , the work, the baby- and then I found out my husband was having an affair. I ran away”(55). The stereotypical society makes everything challenging for a lady. Lodging was simply not available, “because Uzma is female, Uzma is Muslim, Uzma is single, Uzma is foreign, Uzma is alone, Uzma is an actress, and you know what they say about struggling actresses” (23). The episode of Baby Kalki and the attendants of the Kalki Party is a realistic

representation of contemporary politics and political agendas. The use of alluring manifestoes and religious polarization has been among the many strategies employed to win elections in India. The manifesto of the Kalki Party reads:

They believe that they are the superhumans Kalki is supposed to lead, the guardians he will reward Until then, the Kalki Party will fight his battles on his behalf: they promise to destroy terrorism, Communism, the internet, the English language, Pakistan, bikinis, China, Hollywood, the entire Arab world and women's jeans. (90)

Basu also attacks on the unethical practice of media houses. The conversation between Namrata and Aman reveals the corrupt condition of news agencies and news. They are making and manipulating news to cater to the prejudices of the majority or to champion the ruling government. Namrata says, "We decide what goes on air based simply on what people want to see, not what they need to know. We're entertainers, not educators" (165).

Aman's infiltration of the internet exposed the evils of society, and his distribution of money among the needy likens him to the legendary hero Robin Hood. He enquires about the drug lords and mafia across the world and gives away all their money to relief agencies. "He takes billions of dollars from companies and individuals all around the world and redistributing property on a scale that would have made Karl Marx rise from the grave and die again from sheer happiness" (130). He hands out money to conservationists, environmentalists, and peace activists. He hacks the email addresses and passwords of the world's wealthiest people and makes huge charitable donations through public announcements on the web to combat AIDS and human trafficking. "He transfers money from defense budget to development projects leaving warning messages to

government officials, bureaucrats, judges, police chiefs all over the world: *This is not your money, don't keep it. If you do, I'll take away yours* (130). The existing corruption in each department is exposed. Aman's aim is like that of a true superhero who thinks for all of humanity. He asserts, *"My aim is slightly different. I'm going to get everyone in the world electricity, food, water, medicine and access to education"*(134). Answering to his consciousness, Aman claims, *"I don't want fame, or money, or anything for my self- I just want to do what I think is right"* (135). Samit Basu here invites a debate on the concept of heroism as well. Does a superhero have the duty to interfere in others' lives? Do they have the rights? What might happen when a superhero attempts to change the world for the better, even with the best intentions? Super-heroism, *Turbulence* tells us, is subjective, and ultimately all about power. Aman never tried to make the world a better place before he gained his power. He did not volunteer for major relief efforts or charities, nor did he dedicate his life to helping others. *"And yet prior to this you never lifted a finger to help anyone but yourself"* (135). Now, he perceives himself as a superhero; however, he sees the world as his problem to solve, using his personal solution as the answer. Other characters, including the main villain, have similar views. Here, the line between good and evil, brave and cowardly, right and wrong, is not as smooth as in some other superhero stories. Is it really the hero's duty to change the world? Basu suggests that we all have duties and responsibilities to bring positive change in the world. Each individual is a hero, and one should not wait for a miracle to happen or for a superhero to come, but should exercise one's own power to improve human lives. One should be ready to face challenges and dire consequences on the path of change, where firmness and positivity are the mantras of life. Aman's distribution of money went wrong, but he does not abandon the path of justice and humanity. Basu writes:

In several countries people responsible for the funds Aman has appropriated for noble causes have vanished; the money is missing. At least two hundred have been killed, thirty of who might have committed suicide. . . . Aman's victims have not taken their financial losses as a sign to begin leading simpler, purer lives; they have simply resolved to make more money, quickly and brutally. (210-211)

A superhero and his or her subjective decisions may invite calamity, but on a larger scale, persistence and resilience are the keys to success. In a nutshell, we observe that Basu has chosen real humans with extraordinary traits to highlight the real issues and challenges of society. Here, heroes are fighting against real causes and real people rather than aliens and non-terrestrial calamities. Basu has expertly used the fantasy and reality to give a thrilling experience to his readers. He highlights the essential role of superheroes, narrow nationalism, and human concern, and invites everyone to act and react against social evils instead of waiting for some unearthly intervention to curb and control them.

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